

The Puzzle of Gender and Authoritarianism in Saudi Arabia

Madawi Al-Rasheed

Madawi Al-Rasheed is a Visiting Professor at the Middle East Centre, the London School of Economics and Political Science and a Fellow of the British Academy. She is the author of The Son King: Reform and Repression in Saudi Arabia (Oxford University Press 2021), among other publications. Email: m.al-rasheed@lse.ac.uk.

The puzzle of empowering women while repression continues is not unique to Saudi Arabia. Dictatorship is not only about torture and prison cells. It invariably also deploys soft power. The Saudi state uses women to consolidate authoritarian rule, demonstrate piety or secular modernity. The Saudi state demonstrates how women's rights are instrumentalized to create a façade of democratic progress while masking deeper autocratic entrenchment.

Since 2017, Saudi Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman (MBS) has adopted the playbook of a previous generation of autocratic presidents and monarchs, like Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, Kemal Ataturk, and Habib Bourguiba, all of whom championed the emancipation of women. He lifted the ban on women driving, expanded women's employment, and loosened the guardianship rules, all of which had previously crippled women's emancipation. At the same time, he put dissidents in prison, including women who campaigned for gender reforms, and even pursued critics abroad, murdering journalist, Jamal Khashoggi, in the Saudi consulate in Istanbul in 2018. On the surface, the contradiction appears puzzling: violently suppressing democracy while implementing policies that expand women's rights and empowerment.

Observers of Saudi politics oscillate between those who see the crown prince as a ruthless autocrat and those who praise him as a great reformer. This polarised image conceals a complex reality, namely the relationship between autocracy and gender. MBS is simply using gender reform and the emancipation of women as a platform to achieve several objectives.

Like many other countries, Saudi Arabia has experienced the rise of Islamists, whose exclusive gender policies were enforced and supported by the state for several decades. The state-controlled Wahhabi clerics kept women locked in patriarchal structures since the foundation of the state in 1932. While many Saudi women willingly endorsed Wahhabism, in recent times many amongst them felt that this state-sponsored religious ideology went too far in restricting their choices. Since the 1990s, the state began to worry about the rise of militant Islamism. One way to divide the constituency and turn it against militant Islamism was to launch a gender war between men and women. Women were depicted as not only the victims but also the 'warriors' who should be enlisted to fight the Islamist gender agenda on behalf of the state and its security agencies. The state became an opportunistic rather than an honest arbiter between women and the clerics, thus sending

the message that without the state, the clerics and the Islamists would spread even more restrictions and repression against women. The Saudi absolute monarchy became a champion of women's causes against Islamist terror, while at the same time repressing any impulse towards democracy. The crown prince simply used women as a weapon against the Islamists.

While previous kings, above all King Faisal (d.1975) had enforced religious nationalism that narrated the nation in strictly Wahhabi language, the crown prince adopted popular nationalism. The first emphasized the piety of the nation and insisted on the invisibility of women. The second reversed the situation as the visibility of women became the symbol of a modern Saudi nation. To project an image of an open and modern society, the crown prince allowed women to penetrate what used to be all-male public spaces.

The new Saudi nationalism continues to be xenophobic but also endorses neoliberal feminism, in which women need to be visible, beautiful and fully immersed in consumerism. The crown prince ushered a new era of 'Saudi women influencers,' assisted by an army of foreign participants whose on-line promotion of Saudi tourism heritage sites is accompanied by images of women dressed in flowing kaftans and swim wear. The impulse to diversify the oil-based economy requires not only foreign investment but also free access to women-friendly tourism. Saudi women have to be seen as part of global trends in fashion and consumption. They also need to be employed in economic sectors that attract foreign capital. As a result, women benefit while promoting the national narrative about modernity.

As the Saudi leadership promotes the emancipation of women, it is unclear whether this will gradually lead to greater democratic governance. On the contrary, empowering women has contributed to the consolidation of authoritarianism in Saudi Arabia. ♦